

DIGITAL SECURITY VERSUS PRIVATE INFORMATION

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Abstract— This paper demonstrates digital security vs. private information. Digital security can be considered a global security agenda that may concern protecting states and citizens from the misuse of sensitive information. By using privacy and security measures, an organization can manage the security threats associated with it. Moreover, it can be a vital part of the organization because it prevents financial and reputational damage for any organization.

This report aimed to understand the details of digital security and the issue related to the same in terms of handling private information. It sets the objectives and background to the study in the introduction section. It then went on to analyze the methodology section. A mix of primary and secondary research was used in this project, using survey and thematic analysis. The research paper then collected data and analyzed the same with the help of MS Excel graphs and charts and peer-reviewed journals and articles.

This report is prepared to meet the digital economy and manage the digital security and privacy risk for various organizations' social and economic prosperity. This paper discusses the critical dimensional areas towards digital security to connect with the digital environment and privacy of the information technologies. This paper has been articulated risk management by analyzing the possible threat areas to realize the current situation. It came up with the knowledge that digital security has the chance of causing significant issues while storing and securing private information.

Keywords: Digital security, encryption, RFID, risk assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Introduction

The process of developing digital security has become a significant necessity in recent times. The main reason for this lies in the overuse of technology in every aspect of businesses [1]. This is mainly because current cybercrime and attacks have made headlines that can jeopardize ordinary people's trust in sharing information online. This project research shall focus on the same. First, it shall set the objectives and background of the study. Second, it shall also discuss the literature review and the

methodology for conducting the research. Finally, it shall conduct and analyze data.

Problem Statement

The problem statement of the project associates with the idea of digital security and the storage of private information in companies while analyzing the risks of the same in digital security.

Objectives

- To analyze the digital security issues in companies
- To explore the threats to private information management
- To evaluate the failure of digital security to protect private information
- To come up with strategies for mitigating the risks

Research Questions

1. What are the digital security issues in companies?
2. What are the threats to private information management?
3. What are the chances of failure of digital security to protect private information?
4. What are the strategies for mitigating the risks?

Research Background

The background of the study is associated with the concept of digital security for the private information shared on the digital platform. The concept of digital security is a collective term describing the details of the resources employed for protecting the online identity, data, and other assets. These tools might include web services, software, smartphones, SIM cards, secured personal devices, and biometrics [2]. The primary purpose is to secure the online and digital identity and presence of the individuals. The use of digital security measures has generated growing significantly since the online and digital presence of individuals is more important than their offline presence. In addition, the increase in cybercrime and attacks has increased the measures of cybersecurity.

However, the difference between digital and cybersecurity might be considered. While the former involves protecting the online presence, the latter covers more grounds, including entire networks, computer systems, and other digital components. Therefore, cyber protection and security are more complex and challenging jobs than digital security protection [3]. Companies use the same with the help of various steps and measures. They ensure to look after the generation of awareness among the employees regarding the necessity for this security.

The use of processes such as web filtering and firewalls are also significant parts of the same.

Research Rationale

Companies are taking a growing interest in incorporating digital techniques for the growth and development of their businesses. In this regard, they have the role of undertaking the required measures to avoid the chances of risks and threats within their businesses in the longer term [4]. The use of digital security measures might be helpful for the companies to manage and secure the digital and online identities of both employers and employees working for the companies. They are also capable of protecting the information of the customers shared online.

Therefore, the choice of the research project might be helpful for the business owners planning to install digital security within their operations. The development of the overall digital security systems might be a long and complex process. Moreover, it is different for every company. Thus, company owners might benefit from the study by analyzing the various strategies essential in digital security. They might come to learn about the ways and means of developing the settings of digital security. They might also learn about the risks and threats of digital security in protecting private information in employees and customers and taking precautions against it.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Privacy and security are interrelated with each other. Privacy is associated with any kind of right which may control some personal information. Privacy can be maintained by using several privacy policies related to any organization [5]. On the other hand, security means how any organization can protect the information. Digital security and privacy policy can be considered the priority of different public policies in the era of a data-dependent economy. The main challenge of business, government, and other organizations are to manage the risks related to the private information of any organization. A brief overview of digital security and private information will be discussed [6]. After that, it will discuss associated risks and mitigating procedures of those risks. Then, it will examine the evaluation of the failure of digital security, followed by the literature gap.

Overview of Digital Security and Private Information

Digital security is the concept as the collective term for describing the resources need to employ for protecting online data, identity, and other such vital assets. However, this tool is associated with antivirus, secure personal devices, web services, and biometrics [7]. Digital security is the process of protecting online identity. Digital security is essential to trust in this digital age. Within this environment, digital security is the policy and framework that proved the essential and practical principles to address without restricting use, the openness of digital

technology, and dynamic nature without inhibiting the potential to foster innovation to the social technologies.

Moreover, privacy and security are related to each other. Privacy relates to the rights for controlling the personal information for how to use. These two aspects of security and privacy overlap in the connected world [8]. According to the literature, it has been seen over the banking industry to differentiate these two concepts. However, privacy, as well as security, must have to be maintained. Organizations use the customer's private information to marinate the database for the operations and provide the services and products. Therefore, they need to be focused on protecting those data.

Different types of digital security have been seen in this digital world which is offering a wide choice for the defense method such that-

- **Current and updated firewall:** firewall is considered as the network device that can monitor the packets going out and into the blocks and networks or by allowing them accordingly. However, it has been set for defining the permissible traffics [9]. In addition, the firewalls need to be updated to ensure digital security. Hence, it has been used to protect the information system within this organization's database to enhance the activation of services appropriately.
- **Antivirus software:** Viruses can be delivered by malware and another malicious system used to infect the organization data and bring the system towards the screening halt. However, an antivirus detects and uses for cleaning all those infections to keep out the suspicious aspects regarding securing the private information and isolates those likely threats.
- **Remote monitoring software:** Remote monitoring may allow the data security team to collect the information; oversee all the hardware and applications by diagnosing problems remotely [10]. However, remote monitoring software provides the conveniences and flexibility to enable the administrators to solve those implications from anywhere.
- **Proxies:** proxies are commonly known as the digital security tool that can bridge the gap between the internet and users while using the rule to filter in line with those organizations' information technology policies. However, proxies block those dangerous websites and leverage the possible authentication system to control the access and monitor the usage. In addition, this server generally acts as the web filter and firewall to connect the shared network and caching the data to boost up the standard request.
- **Vulnerability scanner:** A vulnerability scanner is a concept for inspection to the potential points that can exploit the computer network for identifying the security holes. However, vulnerability has been used to classify and detect a system's weakness in a computer, communication equipment, and networks and predict countermeasure effectiveness [11]. The organization system may use this tool for evaluating, detecting, and managing that weak spot. The information technology security team may use

this scanner for both their internal system and web applications.

Associated Risks

According to the literature, a digital security risk is an event and action that may damage computer hardware, software, and private data or information in the organizations. Understanding all the existing digital security may help design the proper decisive mitigation plan regarding the security risk [12]. However, any size of business both small and more prominent has been exposed with several digital risks can cause some damage for the development of business or organizations. Here some of the digital risks that are associated with the enterprises or businesses are discussed below-

- **Data risk:** however, data is concerned with thriving the engine. Those are knowledge-based economies for operating the industry or business; management needs to ensure that the business data is stored in safe hands [13]. However, the risk of data is associated with the misuse of sensitive business data and essential customer data.
- **Cybersecurity risk:** while connecting with the internet for business, there is no possible way to eliminate this risk. This kind of risk is evolving intuitively and rapidly; however, the most common cyber risks are ransomware, DDOS attack, and compromised network.
- **Reputational risks:** company valuation has been decreasing significantly for selling out the version of business. The company needs to consider the reputational risk for making a well-revised plan for avoiding or accepting the risks [14]. Reputation-based security is the security mechanism that can classify all the essential files based on the safety of the inherently garnered reputations to those organizations. However, this can make it possible by identifying and predicting the safety of the files based on the widespread use towards the wide community users.
- **Talent storage and cultural risk:** the lack of a skillful workforce can slow down the business growth from the expected level. The organization should have to hire a skilled or knowledgeable team to support the current projects. Even corporate culture has a significant impact on the success of the digital security plan [15]. Organization culture has been associated with the values, beliefs, and attitude may drive the team member behaviors while protecting and defending the organization of business from vulnerable attacks. Though work culture is frequently changing, those are opting towards the short-term role of contract or freelancing.
- **Privacy risk:** while storing personally identifiable information for business purposes, the security team needs to have this process in place by describing it correctly, storing it, and securing the identifiable information personally collected from several users or customers. The organization should have to look at the privacy laws by describing how they should deal with sensitive personal information.

- **Third-party risk:** third party risk is considered as the potential threat of the digital security concept those are presented to the employees of the organization or sensitive customer data, organization process or operation, and financial information [16]. These are from the organization's supply chain and the other outside parties providing services and their products and having access to the privileged system. Regulatory and violations are intensified globally, and reputational damage, systemic events, and financial dependence are associated with this kind of risk.
- **Technology risk:** this kind of risk is potential for any failure regarding the technological aspects to disrupt the business. However, companies face many different types of technological risks associated with cyberattacks, service outages, password theft, SQL injections, and more. Software defects, floods at the center of data, and tripping over the power cords are considered the technical risk associated with the digital risk to the data or application for the information technology that harms the business operations.
- **Artificial intelligence risk:** It is one of the significant digital security risks that the researcher has identified. Towards the artificial system, this kind of risk is the potential of the adversaries while compromising the integrity of the process of decision making [17]. Therefore, it may not make the choices that the designer has been expected or desired.
- **Compliance's risk:** security compliances are generally based on the requirement of external sources rather than objective to risk management of own organization business. However, the compliance risk is associated with the meeting of various controls for protecting the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of essential data. In addition, this kind of risk is dealing with the environmental damage and pollutions of the operation of organizations.

Mitigation Procedure

Here, lots of digital security risk has been discussed those are associated with the personal information. To ensure organizational security in digital aspects, there are lots of mitigation strategies have been developed below-

- **Identifying the key assets:** the organization should maintain its strategies to mitigate all those challenging risks. However, implementing the governance risks and the strategy to the compliances might be helpful that can be defined as the organizational approaches across the best three critical practices of the governance, compliances, and risk management. To correctly manage the digital risks, the company should identify the organization's critical assets [18]. First, however, thinking about the possible ways that might be exposed as vulnerable threats. Moreover, this identification is the key asset for successfully identifying the vulnerabilities and nature of potential attacks.
- **Understanding the potential threats:** By understanding the potential threats, the company needs to understand the threat. There are many available frameworks to help the

organization understand the setup as the defense against real-world threats [19]. Furthermore, prioritize threats to attacks related to the shortest path is needed whenever hackers try to use those organizational exposed login credentials to overtake the accounts by impersonating their brands.

- **Monitoring the unwanted exposure:** After detecting the exposed assets, companies or organizations need to consider the possible sources for any of the unwanted online exposure, such as paste sites, git repositories, online file-sharing misconfigured services, criminal forums, dark we-pages, and social media.
- **Taking action to protect against the risks:** online exposure identification is an important aspect that can be used as the mitigation strategy for the organizational digital security risk associated with the customer or employee personal information [20]. There are three approaches to mitigate those risks included with tactical, strategic, and operational.

Evaluation of the Failure of Digital Security

According to Chen *et al.* [21], one of the significant issues cybersecurity leaders face is the costs of some significant incidents to other stakeholders within their organization. Some elements may have a straight impact, such as costs associated with replacing physical IT assets or loss of revenue from their business activities which may not be established during the outage [22]. Nevertheless, others are challenging to establish. Companies are failed to implement digital security because they are not determining their effectiveness. It has been seen that 80% of the organizations failed to include business users in cybersecurity purchase decisions. They do not include any high-powered committee to evaluate the business impact and risks related to cybersecurity investments. Third-party organizations may perform detailed investments in cybersecurity technologies without measuring the effectiveness of those technologies. 80% of companies fail to communicate with business stakeholders regarding cybersecurity issues [23].

According to Ioane, Knibbs, and Tudor [24], it has been observed that two-third of the cyber-attacks may target small and medium-scale organizations. It happens because hackers often exploit smaller organizations with a lack of resources to search for data shared with large organizations. Digital security efforts can be measured by using Security Benchmark Index Survey [25]. It provides a detailed overview regarding the security benchmark index of an organization. This index helps the organizations to measure their position compared to their peers. By using their free and in-depth resources, companies can protect their critical systems and sensitive information. For assessing the digital security of any organization, a risk assessment needs to be done. Then, they need to collect different kinds of information regarding their digital security policies and procedure of maintaining security to the computer systems, computer networks, email, and much other software [26]. After that, they need to identify and document different internal and external threats. It may involve several tactics, techniques, and procedures used for several target

organizations. For assessing the vulnerabilities, they may use different tools by which they can scan their networks and determine what services they are executing.

According to Kumar and Roy [27], it helps to check whether there is any updated software available within the organization and search for well-known vulnerabilities. The IT administrator may use several tools to execute the pre-defined vulnerabilities against a particular system and use brute force attacks against the end-users [28]. They may appoint a security specialist to measure the resilience of the organization by using penetration testing. After that, they need to perform business impact analysis to determine several impacts of different consequences of digital security threats. Consequences can be financial, operational, and reputational. They need to create a business continuity plan or resilience plan [29]. They must have a clear picture regarding costs associated with the failures of IT or in business operations. After getting a clear idea regarding the potential impact of digital security, they can prioritize resolving the immediate flaws in cybersecurity attacks. If the company authority needs to make some changes to the system security, they need to test these to check whether they negatively impact other systems. As the staff can be considered the most security liability, they need to ensure several rules and regulations to perform documented policies of the organization. They need to provide regular education to the staff, which can be used to perform their business process.

Literature Gap

After evaluating all the research papers and peer-reviewed journals, it has been found that most of the researchers have done theoretical research on the digital security and privacy of information. However, they do not provide any detailed discussion regarding any practical work about any organization's digital security and privacy [30]. This research work does not provide a detailed overview of the risk analysis about different digital security threats of any organization. Further, it does not offer a detailed overview of the business continuity plan and disaster recovery plan to mitigate the risks of digital security and privacy of information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, digital security is considered the most vital part of any organization. It protects all data and information of any organization. It includes lots of sensitive information, personally identifiable information, intellectual property, data, and governmental information system. Without a proper digital security plan, it is hardly possible for any organization to combat data breaches. Therefore, companies need to educate their staff about digital security to easily tackle cybersecurity threats such as phishing, social engineering attacks, and other malware attacks to steal sensitive information of any organization. Furthermore, GDPR and other legal regulations need to be applied to prevent digital security threats.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Onion

Various steps and stages of research might be mandatory while completing the same. In this regard, the research onion by Saunders helps understand the various stages and layers of a research project [31]. The process is comparable with the peeling of the various layers of an onion. While peeling these layers, the researcher comes across the philosophy, strategy, approach, and research. Apart from this, the researcher is also required to specify the processes of data collection, sampling, data analysis, time horizon, etc. These are essential parts of the onion.

Research Philosophy

This is an integral part of the research project. It enables the researcher to evaluate the nature, source, and sources of developing data and knowledge regarding the topic. Pragmatism, positivism, realism, and interpretivism are the four kinds of research philosophy types. This research shall focus on the positivism research philosophy [32]. The benefit of using this philosophy includes the ability of the researcher to incline to factual data and reliable sources while conducting the research. However, this type of philosophy often restricts the role of the researcher in data collection, which might be a limitation.

Research Approach

This is another vital part of the research project and includes all the steps to make broad assumptions about narrowing down the arguments and deductions regarding the same. Three different types of research approaches are commonly used, including deductive, abductive and inductive approaches. The deductive approach of research shall be on focus in this project [33]. This type of approach is often helpful in forming casual bonds between concepts and variables, which might form an advantage for the research. However, it might be a disadvantage since it tends to generalize the findings and analysis of the research.

Research Design

This part of the research project is mandatory for analyzing the details of the entire strategy of the researcher and the logical plan for collecting data and analyzing them for achieving the deliverables. Exploratory and conclusive designs are the two kinds of research designs. The design used in this research is that of the descriptive type of the conclusive research design [34]. This might be advantageous since it takes time to analyze the research for determining the variables associated with the same. The drawbacks of this design might be observed in the form of the inability of the study to analyze and verify the results with statistics.

Data Collection

The process of collecting data is the most critical part of the research. This project shall combine both primary and

secondary sources of research and data collection. The primary research section shall focus on a quantitative survey. In this regard, the researcher shall prepare a questionnaire and target people working in companies to analyze their experience on digital security. The secondary research section shall focus on thematic analysis. The researcher shall break the research topic into several themes and analyze their impact on digital security. The data analysis shall be made based on the collection using both qualitative and quantitative sources of data.

Sample Technique

The sampling technique is again an essential part of the growth and development of research. This is mainly because it is concerned with targeting a specific population in the completion of the research. For this project, the researcher shall use a random sampling technique using the probability method. For the quantitative survey, the questionnaire shall be presented to about 100 employees dealing with digital security. On the other hand, the researcher shall analyze four themes to understand the details of the various attributes and elements of the research topic.

Data Analysis

This is the final and most crucial section of the research project. The researcher tries to analyze and discuss the collected data to develop accurate results against the same. In the primary section, the researcher can generate the participants' opinions against the questionnaire. The analysis shall be done with the help of MS Excel graphs and bars. The researcher shall try to analyze the importance of their opinions based on the majority answers. Further, the researcher shall use scholarly and peer-reviewed journals and articles for analyzing the details of the various themes and discuss their deductions.

Ethical Considerations

The use of ethics and morality is a significant necessity while completing any research work or project. The researchers need to follow a specific form of considerations in this regard. For example, they might follow the Data Protection Act of the UK [35]. Following this, they would have to ensure that they are securing the information present online. They have the role of avoiding the chances of manhandling the information of the participants while keeping their identities anonymous. Furthermore, they need to ensure that the collected data and information are secure on the digital platform by blocking external sources from accessing the same.

Timeline

Activities	Start date	End date	Duration
Finding and setting topic	17-03-2021	19-03-2021	3 days
Problem statement and objectives	22-03-2021	29-03-2021	6 days
Review of literature	30-03-2021	12-04-2021	10 days

Setting the methodology	13-04-2021	22-04-2021	8 days
Conducting survey	23-04-2021	06-05-2021	10 days
Conducting thematic analysis	07-05-2021	24-05-2021	12 days
Analysing data and findings	25-05-2021	14-06-2021	15 days
Final submission	15-06-2021	17-06-2021	3 days

Table 1: Timeline

comprises 31% of the respondents. While about 20% are between 45 and 55 years, only about 10% are older than that. Thus, it can be observed that the survey has considered the opinions of people from most age groups.

Q2. Are you familiar with digital security?

Responses	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Total number of respondents
Yes	65%	65	100
No	9%	9	100
Not sure	26%	26	100

Table 3: Response Regarding Familiarity

IV. RESULTS

Survey

Q1. What is your age group?

Responses	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Total number of respondents
18-30 years	39%	39	100
31-45 years	31%	31	100
46-55 years	20%	20	100
56 years and above	10%	10	100

Table 2: Response Regarding Age

Figure 1: Response Regarding Age

The factor of age might play an essential role in a survey. This is mainly because the thoughts and opinions of the participants might be influenced by their age and experience [36]. According to the answers collected for this question, it might be observed that the majority of the respondents, which is about 39% of them, belong to the age range of 18 and 30 years. This is the youngest age group. Further, the 31-45 years age group

Q2. Are you familiar with digital security?

Figure 2: Response Regarding Familiarity

This question aims at analyzing the details of the familiarity of the participants with digital security. It is a known fact that most companies in recent times use digital security within their services [37]. This is evident in the responses, as most participants have revealed that they are familiar with digital security. This is nearly 65% of the participants. On the other hand, about 9% of them are not familiar with the concept, while 26% are unsure of their response. Thus, it can be deduced that most employees working in the professional arena are aware of digital security.

Q3. Are you satisfied with the digital security in your company?

Responses	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Total number of respondents
Highly satisfied	25%	25	100
Satisfied	39%	39	100
Dissatisfied	25%	25	100
Highly dissatisfied	11%	11	100

Table 4: Response Regarding Satisfaction with Digital Security

Q3. Are you satisfied with the digital security in your company?

Figure 3: Response Regarding Satisfaction with Digital Security

This question aims to understand if the participants are satisfied with the current provision of digital security within their companies. Even though companies resort to developing digital security, cyber-attacks and crimes are still making headlines [38]. According to the participants' opinions, most of them are satisfied moderately, about 39%. About 25% of them are delighted with the use of digital security in their companies. However, it might be observed that 25% of them are dissatisfied with the same, while 11% are highly dissatisfied. This reveals that employees need more assurance for their information security.

Q4. Do you feel that private information has risks in digital security?

Responses	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Total number of respondents
Highly agreed	29%	29	100
Agreed	43%	43	100
Disagreed	15%	15	100
Highly disagreed	11%	11	100

Table 5: Response Regarding Satisfaction with Digital Security

Q4. Do you feel that private information has risks in digital security?

Figure 4: Response Regarding Satisfaction with Digital Security

This question aims at identifying the opinions of the employees regarding the risks associated with digital security. This is mainly because it often becomes difficult for the digital security tools to monitor every aspect of security and information, which might leave gaps for threats to enter [39]. In this regard, about 43% have agreed to the threats, with 29% agreeing strongly. While 15% of them disagree with the chances of risks, 11% have disagreed strongly. However, it might be observed that the chances of risks are still high in digital security.

Q5. Do you wish to bring about improvement in digital technology?

Responses	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Total number of respondents
Yes	58%	58	100
No	12%	12	100
Not sure	30%	30	100

Table 6: Response Regarding Improvement

Q5. Do you wish to bring about improvement in digital technology?

Figure 5: Response Regarding Improvement

The idea of improvement refers to the participants' choices for changes in digital security in the future. The reason is that digital security has so far not been able to guarantee complete security against cyber threats [40]. The majority of the participants reveal that they wish to bring about changes and improvements in digital security, which is about 58% of them. On the other hand, about 12% did not feel the need for improvement, while 30% were unsure. Thus, it can be stated that the participants wish to bring about changes within their use of digital security.

Thematic Analysis

Theme 1: Digital security issues in companies

Digital security is essential within the companies to collect, securely store and adequately protect user or employees, customer data, and proprietary secrets. It has been analyzed that dangerous damage of the company's brand and reducing the

quality of the product for their produces for getting the proper revenue and profitability of the business [41]. However, digital security is the critical business function to maintain personal information. However, non-core competencies remain for boards with a significant number. Therefore, researchers have been suggesting not reporting directly regarding these aspects of digital security to the company's CEO and reducing effectiveness.

According to the thematic analysis, digital security is not just a technological issue about having the latest and advanced security software. It is considered the most significant vulnerability and the potential best defense [42]. Most of the companies from different sectors would have regarding this cybercrime that laid in the regular practices and awareness of their companies employees. Researchers know the majority within the firms are aware of those vulnerabilities and develop the approaches and processes to make sure not to fall victim to digital criminals.

Apart from that, attacks are still occurring over those firms using more advanced security, unfortunately, and even successfully by those attackers. However, it has been analyzed that law firms usually have such insurance to protect their customer's financial losses [43]. Cybercrimes happen due to the reason for money where most of the wealthy clients are associated. Even if recovering the money eventually, stress and impact are involved that is a significant accident for destroying the organization brand value or reputation. Moreover, the organization must have to be focused on digital security to secure the private information associated with the high amount of financial value.

Theme 2: Ways of handling private information

Companies usually have the role of handling the bulk of private information. These might belong to employers, employees, and customers. They, therefore, have the role of handling and maintaining the same. The development of the security settings is vital for managing and handling private information within the professional sector [44]. They try to prioritize confidential information and build their security settings against the same. For instance, the customers' payment and online banking information can be more valuable than the identities and credentials of the employees. They, therefore, need to prioritize the same.

Companies naturally have an additional responsibility when they are trying to protect private information. They need to ensure that they conduct a risk assessment to avoid data theft and security issues. They further try to monitor the data and the activities of the employees in handling the same [45]. If they find any discrepancies with handling the data and information, they need to address the same by securing their private information. Finally, the authorities check the progress in data security and management within their services. They need to avoid dissatisfying the customers by showing discrepancies with their data and information.

Theme 3: Risks and threats with digital security

Several risks and threats might occur while operating digital security systems. This is mainly because the individuals conducting cyber-attacks are more powerful and prepared than the digital tools used in securing data and identity online. For instance, they might face the issue of ransomware [46]. This can occur as a form of malware or malicious software attempting to encrypt the data and information of the company. They extort a ransom for releasing an unlock code. Most of such ransomware is delivered with the help of emails. Phishing is another form of risk in digital security systems. It is an attempt to generate sensitive data while posing as a trustworthy contact.

This might occur when a hacker site uses the logo and information of a company to appear as a link to the customers. They offer similar visuals, and customers might provide their payment credentials in this, generating a cyber-attack [47]. The development of the overall concept of hacking is a significant threat to digital security. This is mainly because when individuals gain access to the IT systems of a company from the outside. They try to access the databases and gain the credit card credentials of the customers. This might be a significant blow to the digital security settings of the company.

Theme 4: Mitigation strategies for the risks

Companies have the role of coming up with effective strategies for mitigating these risks and threats. They need to ensure that they know the risks and threats possible within the digital security systems. They need to hire IT professionals and train their employees in advanced IT lessons to help them understand the details of managing security risks [48]. The owners need to strengthen the IT department and enable them to monitor the exercises of the various departments to ensure that they stay away from chances of security issues. They also need to enhance the investment in IT and purchase more tools and software for preventing malware attacks.

Updating the software and tools is another strategy. This might enable companies to avoid using outdated tools. They also need to ensure the endpoint protection of their networks remotely bridged to the devices. The use of firewalls and antivirus tools might help prevent some of the most common types of cyberattacks [49]. Recently, the use of proper storage and backup systems has gained popularity. Companies might use cloud storage settings to keep their data and information protected online. They need to have control access to all the systems and monitor the activities of the employees within the same.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

According to Raheem *et al.* [50], companies should implement legal regulations in an appropriate format to prevent several digital security threats. Company authorities need to provide clear instructions for following the laws and regulations of digital security. Companies need to create IT security frameworks to prevent cyber-attacks effectively. Companies must provide clear instructions to all the staff to maintain that

security policy [51]. They need to promote a trust-based partnership and need to work on improvements at the international level. Companies need to be focused on the critical social and economic activities which may rely on the information infrastructures. This evolution promotes economic and social activities rather than promoting technical risk management activities about digital security and private information. Organizations may use Digital Security Risk Recommendation as a framework that may strengthen the digital security of economic and social activities without reducing several opportunities offered by digital transformation frameworks. Different operators must execute different activities in different sectors and countries depending on similar digital technologies [52]. Therefore, it may be helpful to exploit common vulnerabilities which may be propagated quickly to the operators.

According to Zalisham and Jali [53], the enhancement of the national policy's digital security can be considered the most vital activity, creating discrepancies in several public policies. It is used to increase the complexity of managing the digital security of different critical activities. Because of that, international co-operation is essential to reduce such discrepancies and increase the global efficiencies about several domestic policies [54]. Countries need to take a higher level of security strategy, including clear objectives to improve digital security and resilience of different critical activities. It ensures the consistency level with national risk assessment and other risk specification strategies. Governments need to implement a domestic governance mechanism that allocates specific authority for developing and implementing policies associated with relevant stakeholders. It is used to improve the digital security standards of organizations. A domestic governance mechanism is used to identify any supporting role the government bodies place for national securities and defense [55]. Companies need to implement Computer Emergency Response Team and Computer Incident Response Teams to monitor several recovery measures associated with digital security. Governments need to promote international security standards, methodologies, baseline security manuals, and many others.

They need to share aggregated statistical data from incident reporting with operators and several other actors. National risk assessment provides detailed identification of critical review and their operators, which may take some critical activities into value chain format. Operators must perform a cyclical enterprise risk assessment to detect critical functionality for ensuring some critical activities [56]. For maintaining the privacy of the information, companies should not share personal and sensitive data with any third-party service providers. It may help them prevent digital security threats and maintain the privacy of the organizations' information. They need to implement data encryption standards to keep sensitive information in a secured format. They also need to implement restrictions based on the individual role within any organization.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, digital security versus private information is discussed in a detailed format. It provides a detailed overview regarding digital security and the private information of any organization. This report provides a clear idea regarding several mitigation strategies for the identified risks of digital security. Organizations need to help cybersecurity professionals resolve or mitigate the risks associated with digital security. It has been observed from this paper that most of the work is done in theoretical format. However, it does not provide any idea about several practical implications of digital securities in society. Implementation of a digital security policy helps any organization combat the cybersecurity threats associated with them. It may cause significant changes regarding the competitive environment of the organizations. Legal regulations play a vital role in maintaining cybersecurity standards within any organization. The governments implement legal regulations to protect the privacy-related information of an individual or any organization. The main aim of these acts is to reduce the chances of cybercrime occurring by using digital devices.

To ensure privacy, hacking is considered an illegal activity. The person involved in this crime will be punished. Radio Frequency Identification can also be implemented for maintaining IT security within any organization. It can be used for asset tracking, people tracking, inventory detection, and many others. For this case, a centralized system can be deployed for controlling and transactional operations. It provides real-time operations for maintaining the digital security of any organization. It also provides secure access to a particular space while keeping a record of the user. They need encryption standards for maintaining information security within the organization. Encryption helps to enhance the security feature of any organization and use to keep the sensitive in secret format. Many security algorithms have been introduced and may be used by several companies in this world. Most of the security algorithms are related to ASCII text. Very few algorithms can handle UNICODE text. Nevertheless, in the digital world, UNICODE plays a vital role in digital communication. This paper provides a detailed overview regarding the evaluation of the failure of digital security.

Many companies have failed to implement digital security because of the unavailability of their digital security policy. As a result, staff members may misuse their sensitive information, leading to severe reputational damage for that organization. It also helps hackers to hack the IT systems of an organization very quickly. It can be a severe security threat for any organization. It may have a considerable impact on the national and economic security of a particular country. Digital security can be considered political practice for a particular country by integrating many conceptual and empirical resources.

VII. REFERENCES

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